

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18

Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

Project ‘CarboSeq’

Deliverable 9.5

Enhancing soil organic carbon modelling in agricultural systems: A spatially dynamic multi-model ensemble in Southern Italy

Deliverable 9.5 Enhancing soil organic carbon modelling in agricultural systems: A spatially dynamic multi-model ensemble in Southern Italy

EJP SOIL
European Joint Programme

19
20
21

Due date of deliverable: M50
Actual submission date: 07.01.2025

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 862695.

GENERAL DATA

22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38

Grant Agreement: 862695
Project acronym: EJP SOIL
Programme title: Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils
Programme website: www.ejpsoil.eu
Project title: CarboSeq
Project website: <https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/carboseq>

Start date of the project: February 1st, 2020
Project duration: 60 months
Name of lead contractor: INRAE
Funding source: H2020-SFS-2018-2020 / H2020-SFS-2019-1
Type of action: European Joint Project COFUND

DELIVERABLE NUMBER: 9.5
DELIVERABLE TITLE: Enhancing soil organic carbon modelling in agricultural systems: A spatially dynamic multi-model ensemble in Southern Italy
DELIVERABLE TYPE: Manuscript
WORK PACKAGE N: WP9
WORK PACKAGE TITLE: Modelling
DELIVERABLE LEADER: CREA, Italy
AUTHOR: Andrenelli M.C., Bellocchi G. *, Di Bene C., Ferchaud F., Napoli R., Raynal H., Farina, R.
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14609796

LICENSE CC BY 4.0

DISSEMINATION LEVEL: CO/PU

39

40 **ABSTRACT**

41

42 This study provides an assessment of soil organic carbon (SOC) models in agricultural systems,
43 emphasising the presence of crop rotation systems. Our multi-step analysis employs diverse
44 models, incorporating plant-derived carbon inputs in agro-ecosystems. With territorial coverage
45 spanning the Foggia Province in southern Italy, our approach includes spatialisation at each
46 step of the protocol. This investigation illuminates intricate SOC dynamics, revealing
47 behaviours under varied conditions. By combining crop rotations, a multi-step protocol and
48 spatialisation, we advance modelling practices and deepen our understanding of SOC's role in
49 sustainable agriculture and climate goals.

50

51 **Enhancing soil organic carbon modelling in agricultural systems:**
52 **A spatially dynamic multi-model ensemble in Southern Italy**

53

54 Andrenelli, M.C., Bellocchi, G. *, Di Bene, C., Ferchaud, F., Napoli, R., Raynal, H., Farina, R.

55

56 * Corresponding author (gianni.bellocchi@inrae.fr)

57

58 **Abstract**

59 This study provides an assessment of soil organic carbon (SOC) models in agricultural systems,
60 emphasising the presence of crop rotation systems. Our multi-step analysis employs diverse
61 models, incorporating plant-derived carbon inputs in agro-ecosystems. With territorial coverage
62 spanning the Foggia Province in southern Italy, our approach includes spatialisation at each
63 step of the protocol. This investigation illuminates intricate SOC dynamics, revealing
64 behaviours under varied conditions. By combining crop rotations, a multi-step protocol and
65 spatialisation, we advance modelling practices and deepen our understanding of SOC's role in
66 sustainable agriculture and climate goals.

67

68 *Keywords:* agricultural systems, multi-model assessment, soil organic carbon, sequestration
69 potential

70

71

72 **Introduction**

73 The sustainable management of soil organic carbon (SOC) is pivotal for bolstering agricultural
74 resilience, curbing carbon (C) losses and preserving ecosystem health (e.g. Xiao et al., 2023).
75 SOC, a cornerstone of soil health, underpins essential functions such as nutrient cycling, water
76 retention and C sequestration (Batjes, 1996; Six et al., 2002; Lal, 2004; Luo et al., 2016).
77 Furthermore, the potential of agricultural soils to contribute to medium- and long-term policy
78 objectives, as exemplified by initiatives like “4/1000 - Soils for Food security and climate”
79 (Minasny et al., 2017; Rodrigues et al., 2021) and C trading schemes (Keenor et al., 2021),
80 underscore the need for reliable methodologies to assess the C sequestration potential of soils.
81 These initiatives are critical in shaping sustainable agricultural practices, highlighting the need
82 for practical tools to guide decision-makers. These methodologies must encompass diverse
83 factors, including land use, management practices, soil type and climate conditions. In pursuit
84 of this goal, simulation models emerge as indispensable tools, enabling the extrapolation of
85 current knowledge across temporal and spatial dimensions while facilitating the exploration of
86 prospective scenarios. However, the extrapolation of C dynamics becomes more intricate when
87 soil is vegetated, as this involves continuous inputs of new organic C from plant residues, root
88 remnants and exudates, which drive microbial activity (e.g. Bell et al., 2014). Additionally,
89 plants significantly influence soil water dynamics and, to some extent, soil temperature,
90 consequently affecting C dynamics (e.g. Brilli et al., 2017). As a result, comparing multiple
91 models under such conditions becomes critical in advancing our ability to predict SOC changes
92 and meet policy goals. The comparison of simulation models under such conditions becomes
93 crucial for advancing our ability to assess and attain policy goals. As data availability and
94 computational resources expand, the SOC modelling community has opportunities to enrich its

95 capabilities and adapt to evolving methodologies, thereby elevating transparency in both the
96 underlying science and modelling practice. Addressing these challenges, the present study
97 focuses on revisiting and benchmarking soil C simulation routines in the context of agricultural
98 soils. We propose the use of multi-model ensembles to reduce the uncertainties associated with
99 individual model structures and enhance the accuracy of predictions (Riggers et al., 2019).
100 Amidst this context, there is a concerted effort to confront the inherent uncertainties in
101 modelling outcomes, recognising that robustly taking model-based evidence can form a solid
102 foundation for policy decisions. Given the critical relationship between agricultural practices
103 and SOC dynamics, (Smith et al., 1997; Falloon and Smith, 2002; Gottschalk et al., 2012; Todd-
104 Brown et al., 2013), our study aims to generate data that can directly inform sustainable land
105 management and policy frameworks at both regional and national levels. In particular, within
106 field conditions, the quantity of C input from crops not only shapes SOC stocks but also
107 influences the rate of SOC mineralisation (Mary et al., 2020).

108 Over time, process-based models have evolved to capture the complex SOC dynamics within
109 agricultural systems. These models incorporate innovative methodologies, enabling
110 comparative assessments that account for the effect of agronomic practices like tillage,
111 fertilisers and crop types (Smith et al., 2001; Wieder et al., 2013, 2014). This evolution reflects
112 the growing recognition of the need to assess and mitigate the adverse environmental impacts
113 of agriculture. While models developed between 2010 and 2021 primarily focussed on soil and
114 ecosystem-level processes, likely due to data availability at specific spatial scales, there is an
115 emerging emphasis on local-scale predictions, meeting the rising demand for models providing
116 decision support to enhance SOC sequestration (Le Noël et al., 2023). With varying
117 assumptions, spatial resolutions and input requirements (e.g. Shi et al., 2018), these models

118 have yet to undergo comprehensive scrutiny of their performance across real-world scenarios.
119 We aim to address this gap by accounting for spatial variability and evaluating the effectiveness
120 of model ensembles in comparison to individual models (Snyder et al., 2009; Rumpel and
121 Kögel-Knabner, 2011; Martin et al., 2021).

122 With the aim of establishing a framework for implementing model ensembles at a regional
123 level, particularly for evaluating SOC-sequestration potentials through Geographical
124 Information System (GIS)-based analysis and fulfilling the requirements of higher tier
125 approaches (e.g. Tier 3; IPCC, 2006), this study is centred on a comparative analysis of diverse
126 SOC models within the context of crop rotations in a southern Italian pilot area. Our objectives
127 are threefold: unveiling SOC dynamics in genuine agricultural settings, highlighting the
128 importance of spatial performance assessment through territorial analysis and exploring the
129 enhanced value gained from employing model ensembles compared to individual models (e.g.
130 Luo et al., 2011). In the wake of multi-model ensemble studies (Ehrhardt et al., 2018; Sándor
131 et al., 2020; Farina et al., 2021; Pulina et al., 2022), our study evaluates the performance of a
132 multi-model ensemble to capture the collective predictive power of various models, thereby
133 mitigating the limitations intrinsic to representing SOC dynamics with a single-model (e.g.
134 Aiteew et al., 2023).

135 Unlike prior studies focused on simplified systems, our research explores the complexity of
136 real-world agricultural landscapes, particularly crop rotations in southern Italy (Ogle et al.,
137 2005). The model inter-comparison framework includes four process-based models, accounting
138 for soil properties and using C inputs from plants as external factors or explicitly simulate plant
139 growth and resulting C input into soils. While existing studies often examine simplified
140 systems, our research explores the challenges and opportunities that genuine agricultural

141 scenarios present (Luo et al., 2010), thereby enhancing the realism of our findings. This adds a
142 new dimension to SOC modelling, potentially making the results more applicable to regional
143 decision-making on SOC management. Additionally, we pioneer the incorporation of spatial
144 performance analysis into SOC ensemble modelling, leveraging a spatially explicit database
145 containing soil, land use and climate data encompassing 33 carefully filtered soil profiles
146 distributed across the Foggia province, Apulia region, southern Italy (Bleuler et al., 2017).
147 Incorporating the spatial dimension allows for a more accurate understanding of SOC dynamics
148 across diverse agricultural conditions. The inclusion of the spatial dimension into this study is
149 essential for capturing the genuine complexity of agricultural landscapes (e.g. Guo and Gifford,
150 2002; Mirchooli et al., 2020). With the utilisation of a long-term sampling survey dataset, our
151 study specifically aims to anticipate the impact of land use and land use change across the
152 province of Foggia on the temporal and spatial dynamics of SOC, with SOC contents
153 normalised to a 0.3-m soil depth in all profiles between 1994 and 2004 (Beuler et al., 2017).
154 Moreover, our model outputs are expected to support region-specific recommendations on land
155 use practices, improving the practical relevance of our findings.

156 Furthermore, the study seeks to explore potential management strategies within this context by
157 linking SOC ensemble modelling with a spatially explicit database encompassing soil, land use
158 and climate data. Our research introduces several innovative elements, notably the application
159 of SOC ensemble modelling to Mediterranean cropping systems, which remain understudied in
160 comparison to other regions. The novelty of this research lies in applying SOC ensemble
161 modelling on a spatial scale, tailored to simulate SOC dynamics in typical Mediterranean
162 cropping systems. An additional innovative facet involves incorporating actual annual crop
163 rotations at each location to estimate C inputs into the soil. Diverging from an earlier single-

164 model study (Farina et al., 2017), this approach draws on the collective insights of an ensemble
165 of models, thereby yielding a more comprehensive understanding of the impacts of land use
166 and land use change on SOC dynamics. This offers new insights into SOC dynamics that could
167 inform both local and broader-scale land management practices.

168 Our study also addresses data limitations by acknowledging the realism of our dataset, which
169 mirrors the constraints faced by modellers in the real world (Zhang et al., 2007; Smith et al.,
170 2016). Rather than aiming for exhaustive evaluations, we focus on practical, applicable insights
171 that bridge the gap between scientific rigour and real-world feasibility. This work extends the
172 existing SOC modelling in the study area (Farina et al., 2017) to ensemble modelling. Prior
173 research evaluated a single SOC model, RothCN10, a modified version of the original RothC
174 model (Coleman and Jenkinson, 1996, 1999; Jenkinson et al., 1999), suited for simulating SOC
175 dynamics under semi-arid and Mediterranean conditions (Farina et al., 2013). By adopting
176 ensemble modelling, we aim to provide a more comprehensive and reliable assessment of the
177 factors influencing SOC stocks and dynamics. Then, by linking a GIS database containing soil,
178 climate, land use and management data to a SOC simulation model ensemble, and accounting
179 for factors influencing soil C dynamics, we estimate the impacts of land use and management
180 on SOC stocks (after Falloon et al., 2007; Mondini et al., 2012; Lugato et al., 2014; Yagasaki
181 and Shirato, 2014). This approach enables us to assess the sensitivity of specific soil-climate
182 combinations to variations in land use (arable crops or temporary grasslands) and management,
183 spotlighting areas and cropping systems with a higher potential for C sequestration. Capitalising
184 on ensemble modelling, which captures the mean or median response of multiple models,
185 facilitates a comprehensive assessment of C dynamics. We envision that this method could also
186 contribute directly to improving C inventory reporting processes for regulatory frameworks

187 such as the Kyoto Protocol (UNFCCC, 1998) and EU mandates (EU, 2013). In contrast to
188 existing research that often reports mean SOC values based on land use, climate or soil type
189 (Chiti et al., 2012; Mondini et al., 2012), our study adopts a more comprehensive approach,
190 leveraging the collective insights of an ensemble of models.

191

192 **Materials and methods**

193 *Study area*

194 We refer to agricultural areas from the Foggia Province ($41^{\circ} 03' - 41^{\circ} 55' N$; $14^{\circ} 55' - 16^{\circ} 02'$
195 E), located in the Apulia Region of Southern Italy (Fig. 1).

196

197 Fig. 1. Aerial view of the study-area. Red dots indicate soil profiles for which sample data are
198 available.

199

200 The Utilised Agricultural Area (UAA) in this region is representative of typical Southern
201 Mediterranean cultivation systems. The climate is predominantly Mediterranean, characterised
202 by long, hot and dry summers, and short, cold winters. Mean annual rainfall ranges between
203 672 and 778 mm, and mean temperatures vary from 10.9 to 15.2 °C. The region's altitude ranges
204 from 0 to 1151 m a.s.l. The soils of the area are mainly of deep alluvial origin, with a clay or
205 silty clay texture.

206 The main crops include winter cereals (primarily durum wheat), summer irrigated crops
207 (tomatoes), as well as vineyards, olive groves and pastures. Climate data, including mean
208 monthly rainfall, temperature and evapotranspiration, were derived from a 20 km x 20 km grid-
209 based climate dataset available from the Joint Research Centre
210 (<http://mars.jrc.ec.europa.eu/mars/About-us/AGRI4CAST>) and validated using locally
211 observed data.

212 A georeferenced soil database, consisting of 280 soil profiles distributed throughout the Foggia
213 Province, was compiled from two regional soil archives in the CREA soil data repository. These
214 archives were previously used to prepare National soil maps
215 (<http://www.soilmaps.it/ita/cartadeisuoli1.html>). The database includes site characteristics,
216 horizon descriptions and key soil physical-chemical parameters, such as grain size distribution,
217 bulk density, hydrological parameters, pH, cation exchange capacity, SOC concentration and
218 total nitrogen. SOC contents were standardised to a soil depth of 0.3 m across all profiles.

219 For this modelling exercise, a more focused area within the Foggia Province was selected. The
220 data were spatialised to derive a single value for each relevant parameter (clay, silt and sand)
221 for every grid cell, associating initial and final C values with these cells. The model output

222 (SOC) was obtained and assessed using a set of 33 independent data points, overlaid on the
223 spatialised map of soil profiles from 1994.

224 These 33 soil profiles were selected through a filtering process from an initial set of 48 profiles.
225 Tree crop land-uses such as vineyards and olive groves were excluded from the analysis, as
226 they did not align with the target land-use categories. Additionally, 14 profiles were removed
227 from the analysis due to unrealistic changes in SOC values between 1994 and 2004, which
228 could be attributed to potential uncertainties such as differences in sampling locations, variation
229 in sampling and analytical methods, or errors in soil surveys. This filtering process ensured the
230 reliability and accuracy of the final dataset used in the analysis.

231 A comprehensive description of the study area and the data used can be found in Bleuler et al.
232 (2017) and Farina et al. (2017).

233

234 *Data resources and study scope*

235 The study adopted a systematic approach, leveraging diverse datasets across three crucial stages
236 for model execution. The data sources encompassed critical aspects relevant to understanding
237 soil dynamics, including soil profiles for 1994, corresponding data for 2004, land-use
238 information spanning 1990-1993 and 1994-2004, and agricultural data from the Italian Farm
239 Accountancy Data Network (FADN-RICA, <http://rica/public/it/index.php>). The dataset was
240 further enriched through the integration of national statistics database (ISTAT,
241 <https://www.istat.it>) and AGRIT land parcels database (Di Bene et al., 2016). Land use
242 categories considered for the modelling are shown in Table 1.

243

244 Table 1. DPM/RPM ratio^a, carbon input from plant residues and plant cover periods for all crop
245 types according to AGRIT categories used for the modelling exercise.

Land use (crop) ^b	DPM/RPM	C input	Control Plant cover	N fertilisation	Irrigation	Yield
Durum wheat	1.44	1.81	January-June (sowing in November-December)	100 kg N ha ⁻¹	-	3 t ha ⁻¹ (12% H ₂ O)
Tomato	1.44	2.72	Avril-August (transplanting in April)	400 kg N ha ⁻¹	80% of the water holding capacity (~1000 mm [10000 m ³ ha ⁻¹]) between April and August, adjusted on rainfall)	4.34 t DM ha ⁻¹ (about 85 t ha ⁻¹ of green biomass; harvest index 0.65; 0.5 to 3 t DM ha ⁻¹ of crop residues)
Forage crop ^c	1.44	2.19	November-June			1 to few t ha ⁻¹

246 ^a Ratio of readily degradable plant material (DPR) to resistant plant material (RPR).

247 ^b Typical rotation: durum wheat-tomato-durum wheat-tomato-forage crop

248 ^c One-year grass-legume mixture, e.g. oats/wheat/barley/fescue/vetch/pea

249

250 *Simulation models*

251 The simulation study used a systematic methodology to simulate soil organic carbon (SOC)
252 dynamics through three key steps: equilibrium initialization, SOC stock simulation and
253 refinement of accuracy through progressive data integration. This approach allowed each model
254 to capture SOC behaviour under different climate and management scenarios.

255 To achieve this, four process-based models were selected, each of which contributing uniquely
256 to understanding SOC changes. Table 2 provides an overview of the models used, including
257 their versions, C pools, spin-up periods and documentation links for further details. The selected
258 models are integrated within an ensemble modelling framework, which enhances the robustness

259 of predictions by combining outputs from multiple models. The ensemble includes both soil-
 260 focused (AMG, RothC, ECOSSE) and ecosystem-based (STICS) approaches, providing a
 261 balanced methodology for understanding SOC dynamics. The soil-focused models specialize
 262 in capturing belowground carbon processes, such as decomposition of soil organic matter and
 263 carbon inputs from cropping systems. In contrast, STICS, as an ecosystem model, integrates
 264 aboveground interactions and the broader soil-plant-management-atmosphere system. The
 265 ensemble framework ensures that both soil processes and ecosystem-wide factors (such as crop
 266 production, land management practices, and climate) are considered. By combining the
 267 strengths of different models, this integrated ensemble approach offers the potential for more
 268 accurate and robust predictions of SOC dynamics under different environmental and
 269 management conditions. It reduces uncertainties associated with reliance on a single model or
 270 a single type of model (e.g. soil-focused) and ensures a more comprehensive understanding of
 271 both subsurface and ecosystem-wide processes. This structured, multi-model approach allows
 272 each model to contribute complementary perspectives on how SOC stocks respond to
 273 environmental drivers, providing a thorough understanding of C dynamics under different land
 274 use and climate conditions.

275

276 Table 2. Overview of process-based simulation models used.

Model name	Version	C pools	Spin-up	URL or contact for documentation/description	References
AMG	...	2-3	None	https://entrepot.recherche.data.gouv.fr/dataverse/amg_model	Andriulo et al. (1999), Saffih-Hadi and Mary (2008), Clivot et al. (2019), Levavasseur et al. (2020)

ECOSSE	...	5	None	https://www.abdn.ac.uk/staffpages/uploads/soi450/ECOSSE%20User%20manual%20310810.pdf	Smith et al. (2010a, b)
RothC	RothC10 N	4-5	None	https://www.rothamsted.ac.uk/rothamsted-carbon-model-rothc	Coleman and Jenkinson (1999), Farina et al. (2013, 2017), Di Bene et al. (2016)
STICS	9.0	2-4	None	https://stics.inrae.fr	Brisson et al. (1998, 2003, 2008), Coucheney et al. (2015)

277

278 *Model-specific methodology*

279 Each process-based model in this study used different methodologies, tailored to simulate SOC
280 dynamics under different environmental and management conditions. An overview of the
281 specific approaches used for each model is provided below.

282

283 AMG: ...

284

285 RothC: In the initial step, the model was initialised to an equilibrium state, simulating
286 conditions until 1994 with consideration for potential vegetation. Automatic adjustments were
287 made until the SOC stock aligned with the measured stock, establishing a baseline for assessing
288 management and climate effects. The second step involved simulating SOC stock from 1994 to
289 2004, assuming constant C input values based on cropping practices and soil management. The
290 third step enhanced the simulation by incorporating the actual SOC stock value in 2004 and
291 running RothC Program in *inverse mode* to obtain new C input values for different crop
292 sequences and management combinations. These adjusted C input values were then employed
293 to run RothC *in forward mode* (standard procedure), providing SOC stock values for 2004 that

294 best fit the measured ones. In addition, given that RothC simulates SOC stock dynamics
295 exclusively within SOC cycle, the overall SOC stock balance is expressed by the formula:

$$296 \Delta_{\text{SOC stock}} = C_{\text{input}} - C_{\text{CO}_2}$$

297 where $\Delta_{\text{SOC stock}}$ is the difference between 2004 and 1999 SOC stock simulated values, C_{input} is
298 the overall amount of C added to the soil during the considered interval period (1994-2004) and
299 C_{CO_2} represents the simulated loss due to the soil organic matter mineralisation.

300

301 ECOSSE: A similar approach to RothC was adopted when employing ECOSSE. However, as
302 the latter was launched in *limited mode*, the hydrological constants and evapotranspiration data
303 were internally estimated by the model. In contrast, in RothC, the user provided monthly
304 evapotranspiration, while the hydrological constants were estimated using improved
305 pedotransfer functions (Farina et al., 2013). In addition, given that ECOSSE simulates SOC
306 stock dynamics, including crop yield, the overall SOC stock balance differs from that
307 considered in RothC and is expressed by the formula:

$$308 \Delta_{\text{SOC stock}} = C_{\text{input}} - (C_{\text{CO}_2} + C_{\text{yield}})$$

309 where C_{yield} is the simulated C loss due to the harvesting of the crop production.

310

311 STICS: ...

312

313 *Model execution process*

314 Model execution was performed at the cell (profile) level and unfolded in three main steps
315 (Table 3). Each step involved both SOC simulation and spatial interpolation. A central

316 coordination unit was responsible for the integration and analysis of the independently
 317 generated model outputs. The existence of this coordination unit was a key strength of the
 318 modelling framework, ensuring consistency in data integration and analysis of results across
 319 different models and steps.

320

321 Table 3. Overview of sequential model execution steps.

Scope	Step 1: Initialisation (1990-1994)	Step 2: Partial calibration (1994-2004)	Step 3: Full calibration (1994-2004)
Purpose	In the first step, the models are set up by initialising the SOC content, using coarse inputs for land use and climate data. This allows a broad simulation of SOC dynamics over a four-year period.	In the second step, the models are refined by incorporating more detailed land use information at the profile level. This allows the models to better simulate SOC dynamics over a 10-year period.	In the third step, the models are fully calibrated using observed SOC data from 2004. This final calibration helps to further refine the models and to bring the simulated SOC results in line with the real data.
Assessment	The initialisation step serves as a foundational phase, helping to establish baseline SOC values. Although coarse inputs may limit accuracy at this step, it is a common and practical starting point for large-scale models. By relying on historical data and generalised land use inputs, models are able to capture important SOC trends.	This step improves the accuracy of the models by introducing higher resolution inputs, including specific land management practices. It focuses on the period 1994-2004 and captures SOC changes driven by climate and land management.	Calibration with actual SOC data from 2004 ensures the validity of the models. Fine-tuning the models with empirical data corrects discrepancies and improves the predictive ability and reliability of the models under different conditions.
Strengths	This step effectively prepares the models for further refinement and provides an early assessment of SOC trends without requiring highly detailed data for earlier periods.	The introduction of profile-specific data adds much-needed detail, improving the ability of models to simulate real-world SOC dynamics. This increases prediction accuracy and insight into local SOC variations.	Calibration with observed SOC data improves model accuracy and ensures consistency with empirical evidence. This is crucial for the evaluation of model performance and the application of the models in operational scenarios.
Limitations	Coarse inputs may reduce initial accuracy, particularly in capturing fine-scale SOC	While the accuracy improves, the partial calibration lacks a final calibration against actual	Full calibration is limited to 2004 data, which may limit the ability of the models to accurately

variability. Early observed SOC data. A simulate SOC beyond
simulations may complete evaluation this period unless updated
introduce some bias, against empirical calibration data are
which is mitigated in later measurements is still available.
steps. required.

322

323 Data provision was organised in steps to support incremental model refinement. In the first
324 stage (1990-1994), historical data including climate, soil parameters and georeferenced
325 CORINE land cover maps (<http://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/corine-land-cover>) were
326 provided along with daily climate data, initial soil information and historical crop yields. In the
327 second step (1994-2004), more detailed climate, soil and land use management data were
328 introduced for each soil profile. The third step (1994-2004) included similar data provision as
329 the second step, but with the addition of final SOC content during the simulation period. This
330 stepwise refinement of the models ensured that the simulations became increasingly more
331 accurate. By moving from coarse to more detailed inputs, the models were able to capture both
332 broad trends and local variations in SOC dynamics. The models integrated a wide range of data
333 sources, including climate data, land cover maps, and detailed land use and management
334 practices, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing SOC. Operation
335 at the cell (profile) level provided fine-scale spatial resolution, while the multi-decadal time
336 span allowed detailed temporal analysis of SOC dynamics.

337

338 *Spatial interpolation*

339 Spatial interpolation of both the initial organic C stock at equilibrium and the simulated organic
340 C stock for the 2004 was performed using individual model simulations and the multi-model
341 median. This process employed the machine learning Random Forest (RF) algorithm,
342 implemented via the “Ranger” package (Wright and Ziegler, 2017) within a geostatistical

343 spatial approach in R. RF is an ensemble method that constructs multiple decision trees, each
344 trained on a random subset of the data. The final prediction at each location is made by
345 averaging the results of these trees, which enhances accuracy and reduces overfitting (Breiman,
346 2001). For spatial interpolation, RF learns from covariate patterns at sampled locations, such as
347 topography, soil properties, and land cover, and generalizes these patterns to unsampled areas,
348 providing robust estimates of organic C stocks. This approach makes RF particularly well-
349 suited for capturing complex, non-linear relationships between organic C stocks and
350 environmental covariates, which simpler geostatistical methods may struggle to represent
351 effectively (Hengl et al., 2018). The choice of RF over traditional methods, such as kriging or
352 inverse distance weighting, is justified by several key advantages. RF is able to handle a large
353 number of diverse covariates without requiring specific assumptions about the functional
354 relationships between them and the response variable (organic C stocks). In this study, we used
355 a diverse set of landscape covariates, including morphometric parameters from a Digital
356 Elevation Model (DEM), the Soil World Reference Base classification (IUSS-WRB, 2014), and
357 several soil indicators derived from Landsat TM remote sensing imagery (as detailed in Table
358 3). RF can efficiently integrate both continuous and categorical data, automatically selecting
359 the most important variables for prediction, which enhances its performance compared to
360 methods like kriging that rely heavily on spatial autocorrelation and assumptions of stationarity
361 (Grimm et al., 2008). In addition, RF is highly robust to noise and overfitting, a common issue
362 when dealing with large and heterogeneous spatial datasets. The ensemble nature of RF, which
363 aggregates the results from multiple decision trees, minimises the effect of individual noisy data
364 points, leading to more stable and generalisable predictions (Cutler et al., 2007). This is
365 particularly relevant in environmental datasets where measurement errors or incomplete data

366 are common, and methods like kriging may be more sensitive to these issues (Keshtkar et al.,
367 2017). From a computational standpoint, RF is also more scalable and computationally efficient
368 than geostatistical methods like co-kriging, which can become computationally expensive with
369 increasing data size and dimensionality (Li and Heap, 2014). For large-scale spatial
370 interpolation tasks, such as the organic C stock estimation presented here, the efficiency of RF
371 offers significant practical advantages. Furthermore, RF provides variable importance
372 measures, which allow us to assess the relative contributions of different covariates to the
373 predicted organic C stocks, offering additional insights into the factors driving organic C
374 distribution (Prasad et al., 2006).

375 Given these strengths, RF was chosen as the primary interpolation method in this study, with
376 its performance further supported by its ability to account for spatial heterogeneity and complex
377 landscape features across different modelling steps and use-cases. The spatial covariates were
378 initially processed using the Italian TIN DEM at a 10-m resolution (Tarquini et al., 2023), then
379 upscaled using SAGA-GIS (Conrad et al., 2015; version 7.3.0) through a mean value upscaling
380 method, with weights assigned based on cell area. Finally, the covariates were snapped to the
381 EU-DEM grid at a 25-m pixel scale to ensure they accurately represented finer spatial patterns
382 at the site or profile level. The interpolation was applied across three modelling steps and five
383 specific use-cases involving the AWG, RothC, ECOSSE and STICS models, as well as the
384 ensemble median results.

385

386 Table 3. Covariates implemented as predictors in the machine learning Random Forest analysis
387 for spatial interpolation of organic C stocks.

Predictor (covariate)	Description	Reference
	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 862695.	21

Digital (DEM)	Elevation	Model	EU-DEM digital surface model (DSM)	Tarquini et al. (2023)
Slope			Slope percentage (%)	
Cprof			Profile curvature, indicating the shape of the slope profile	Olaya (2009)
TWI			Topographic Wetness Index, representing water accumulation potential	Boehner et al. (2002), Boehner and Selige (2006)
MRVBF/MRRTF			Multiresolution index of valley bottom flatness (MRVBF) and the complementary ridge top flatness (MRRTF)	Gallant and Dowling (2003)
Vdepth			Valley depth, representing the depth of valleys across the terrain	Olaya (2009)
Openness (p or n)			Degree of topographic openness or enclosure of a landscape location (p: positive openness; n: negative openness)	Yokoyama et al. (2002), Prima et al. (2006), Anders et al. (2009)
Devmean			Deviation from mean value, showing the relation of each grid cell to its surrounding neighbourhood	Wilson and Gallant (2000)
WRB_Unit			WRB Working Group - Digital soil map of Foggia Province (CREA-AA National Soil Database)	Fantappiè et al. (2023)
CI (Clay Index)			Clay content index derived from Landsat TM imagery	Hengl (2007)
GSI (Grain Size Index)			Grain size index derived from Landsat TM imagery	Xiao et al. (2006)
NDSI (Normalised Difference Soil Index)			Soil properties index calculated from Landsat TM imagery	Deng et al. (2015)

388

389 Results

390 Evaluation of SOC dynamics

391 **Temporal SOC trends:** Summarise how SOC levels have changed over the 10 year period,

392 showing trends in carbon accumulation or depletion in different soil profiles

393 **Influence of crop rotations:** Compare the effects of crop rotations on SOC dynamics,

394 highlighting how different sequences (e.g. wheat-tomato-fodder) affected SOC stocks

395 **Spatial variability:** Discuss how spatial variation (e.g. soil types, climate, topography)

396 influenced SOC patterns, supported by model results

397 **Drivers of SOC change:** Highlight the main drivers of SOC changes, such as C inputs from

398 crop residues, soil properties and management practices, using model-specific evidence

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 862695.

399

400 *Ensemble performance*

401 **Prediction accuracy:** Report the statistical performance of the ensemble (e.g. root mean square
402 error, correlation coefficient) compared to each model in predicting SOC levels

403 **Uncertainty reduction:** Demonstrate how the ensemble approach reduced uncertainties in
404 predicting SOC stocks compared to individual models, using specific metrics (e.g. box-plots)

405 **Comparative insights:** Highlight differences between models (RothC, AMG, ECOSSE,
406 STICS) and how these differences were mitigated by ensemble averaging

407

408 *Individual versus multi-model ensemble*

409 **Model-specific accuracy:** Identify which models over- or under-predicted SOC stocks and in
410 which circumstances (e.g. certain crop rotations or soil types)

411 **Bias analysis:** Present an analysis of systematic biases in individual models and how the
412 ensemble corrected for these biases

413 **Case studies:** Use specific examples from the Foggia Province to show where individual
414 models failed and how the ensemble approach led to more realistic outcomes

415

416 *Analysis of model residuals*

417 **Model fit evaluation:** Provide a detailed statistical analysis of the residuals from each model
418 and the ensemble, including distribution patterns, potential outliers and areas of significant
419 deviation

420 **Sensitivity analysis:** Examine how sensitive different models were to input variables (e.g. soil
421 texture, crop residue inputs), explaining where and why residuals were largest

422 **Improving model calibration:** Identify areas where model calibration could be refined,
423 especially in cases of extreme under- or over-predictions

424

425 *Spatial interpolation*

426 **Map-based results:** Present interpolated maps showing the spatial distribution of SOC for
427 1994 and 2004. Compare the results from the ensemble with individual models, emphasising
428 areas with significant differences

429 **Hotspots of C sequestration:** Identify regions within the Foggia Province that showed higher
430 potential for SOC sequestration and discuss the implications for land management strategies

431

432

433

434

435

436

437 *Multi-model ensemble for SOC sequestration potential*

438 **Projected SOC sequestration:** Quantify the amount of C sequestered across different soil
 439 profiles and land uses over the 10-year period

440 **SOC sequestration potential by land use:** Compare SOC sequestration rates between crop
 441 types (e.g. wheat, tomatoes, forage) and management practices, showing how they align with
 442 sustainable agriculture goals

443 **Management recommendations:** Provide region-specific recommendations for land use and
 444 management based on model outcomes, discussing which practices (e.g. crop rotations, reduced
 445 tillage) enhance SOC sequestration the most

446

447 **Discussion**

448 ...

449 The study explores how multi-model ensembles can effectively capture soil organic carbon
450 (SOC) dynamics across agricultural systems in Foggia, Southern Italy. Leveraging various
451 models, the research integrates plant-derived carbon contributions, crop rotations, and site-
452 specific calibration to enhance the spatial accuracy and operational applicability of SOC
453 predictions.

454

455 *Calibration and site-specific knowledge*

456 The findings suggest that a basic calibration scenario, using general system knowledge without
457 extensive local data, can yield reliable initial SOC estimates. However, incorporating site-
458 specific calibration refines model accuracy, reflecting localised dynamics such as microclimatic
459 variations, soil properties and crop management practices. This refinement is valuable because
460 as modelling scales increase - moving from single sites to regional or national assessments - the
461 resources required for extensive site-specific calibration may become impractical. Thus, where
462 feasible, site-specific calibration improves the precision of SOC models, aiding in policy and
463 management decisions tailored to local agricultural and environmental conditions.

464

465 *Relevance of the multi-model median (MMM)*

466 A key aspect of this study is the use of a multi-model median (MMM) approach, which
467 combines the outputs of multiple SOC models to produce a central tendency prediction. This
468 MMM method effectively represents the spatial structure of SOC data across the Foggia region,
469 delivering consistently more accurate outputs than single models in each phase of the analysis.

Commented [GB1]: Extreme water stress without organic matter degradation should be discussed, according to Farina et al. (2024, Canadian Journal of Soil Science), long-term experiment in Apulia: extreme temperatures, soil cracks, below wilting point (De Vita et al., 2007), etc.

470 As highlighted by Farina et al. (2020) and recalled by Díaz et al. (2024), a multi-model
471 ensemble of two to four models can provide a reliable MMM estimate, even in cases where data
472 availability is limited. In this study, the MMM approach proved effective in generating detailed
473 spatial insights, particularly at centroids and in regional maps. This supports the value of multi-
474 model approaches in addressing the inherent complexities and uncertainties of SOC modelling
475 at larger spatial scales.

476

477 *Operational implications for large-scale SOC modelling*

478 This study highlights the operational benefits of multi-model ensembles for large-scale SOC
479 modelling where resources and data for calibration may be limited. The multi-step protocol
480 outlined here demonstrates that the integration of crop rotation, spatialisation and a multi-model
481 ensemble approach can provide reliable SOC assessments without the need for exhaustive
482 calibration at each site. Consequently, this methodology provides a practical solution for scaling
483 SOC models, making it operationally feasible to support sustainable agricultural practices
484 across regions while contributing to climate goals through improved carbon sequestration
485 estimates. The protocol of this study can be applied to similar agricultural regions around the
486 world where large-scale SOC modelling is essential for sustainable land management.

487

488 **Summary and conclusion**

489 *Performance of the multi-model median (MMM)*

490 This analysis examined the intricate dynamics of SOC in a southern Italian agricultural
491 landscape, particularly focusing on its interplay with crop rotations. Throughout the study, we

492 underscored the importance of spatial performance assessment and advocate for an expanded
493 approach to multi-model ensemble evaluation, aiming to boost the accuracy of SOC modelling.
494 The MMM consistently outperformed individual models, especially in spatial accuracy, and
495 provided more robust estimates of SOC behaviour across different phases, as supported by key
496 statistical metrics such as model agreement indices and spatial autocorrelation. Ensemble
497 modelling proved to be a particularly powerful tool in this regard, demonstrating statistically
498 significant improvements when validated against observational data from centroids and mapped
499 regions.

500

501 *Challenges and data limitations*

502 It is important to acknowledge the challenges associated with a limited data set, as this
503 introduces a degree of uncertainty into our results. Specific limitations included the lack of
504 regionally calibrated SOC data and incomplete records of site-specific agricultural practices,
505 which in some cases affected model accuracy. The limited availability of comprehensive data
506 highlights the need for modellers to manage this uncertainty, particularly when moving from
507 scientific research to operational applications. To mitigate these challenges, future models
508 could incorporate additional datasets, such as remotely sensed imagery and farmer-reported
509 management data, to enrich site-specific calibration without significantly increasing resource
510 requirements. This approach would contribute to a more nuanced understanding of real-world
511 complexities and provide a stronger basis for refining soil management strategies.

512

513 *Implications for soil science and sustainable agriculture*

514 By bridging the gap between modelling approaches and practical applications, our work has
515 implications for the fields of soil science and sustainable agriculture. Ensemble modelling,
516 within our simplified methodology, provides potential avenues to leverage the benefits of
517 multiple models in the face of limited data. Despite the limited number of models used in this
518 study, the MMM methodology effectively used different model outputs to improve accuracy.
519 Building on the results of the analysis and the practical implications of the findings, our
520 methodological insights, coupled with the characteristics of the study area, aim to catalyse
521 advances in both research methodologies and actionable strategies for sustainable agriculture.

522

523 *Future research and broader applications*

524 The call to expand research efforts to encompass a more diverse range of agricultural landscapes
525 remains an agenda for future investigations. While the specific environmental and agricultural
526 conditions of southern Italy, such as the prevalence of wheat-tomato rotations and the semi-arid
527 climate, limit the direct applicability of these results to other regions, the multi-model
528 framework presented here provides valuable insights for broader applications. Although caution
529 should be exercised in generalising our results, considering the specific context of the southern
530 Italian agricultural landscape, this study underlines the importance of extending research
531 towards other agricultural landscapes and exploring various modelling approaches to enrich the
532 understanding of SOC dynamics at a broader scale. Future research should also assess the
533 interaction between crop-specific rotation practices (e.g. legumes, cover crops) and SOC
534 sequestration to provide more targeted guidance for sustainable land management.

535

536 *Conclusion and recommendations*

537 In summary, the research makes a significant contribution to SOC modelling by demonstrating
538 how a multi-model approach, supported by spatial dynamics and crop rotation data, improves
539 the reliability of SOC estimates. The study provides a practical framework for scaling up SOC
540 models in agricultural contexts, which can support more informed decision making for
541 sustainable agriculture and climate strategies. A key recommendation for scaling up would be
542 to combine localised data collection efforts with advanced modelling techniques such as
543 machine learning, which could improve predictions while limiting the operational burden of
544 extensive site-specific calibrations.

545

546 **Acknowledgements**

547 This study was conducted as part of the EJP Soil CarboSeq project ([https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-](https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/carboseq)
548 [research/carboseq](https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/carboseq)) and we gratefully acknowledge the support provided by the project. We
549 would also like to extend our appreciation to Alessandro Marchetti (CREA-AA, Rome, Italy)
550 for his invaluable assistance in the creation of the dataset, as well as his contribution to the
551 spatialisation and graphical rendering efforts, which significantly enhanced the accuracy and
552 presentation of our findings.

553

554

555 **References**

- 556 Aiteew, K., Rouhiainen, J., Nendel, C., Dechow, R., 2023. Evaluation and optimisation of the
557 soil carbon turnover routine in the MONICA model (version 3.3.1). EGU sphere [preprint],
558 <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2023-760>
- 559 Anders, N., Seijmonsbergen, A., Bouten, W., 2009. Multi-scale and object-oriented image
560 analysis of high-res LiDAR data for geomorphological mapping in Alpine mountains. In:
561 Purves, R., Gruber, S., Hengl, T., Straumann, R. (Eds.), Proceedings of Geomorphometry
562 2009. University of Zurich, pp. 61-65.
- 563 Andriulo, A., Mary, B., Guerif, J., 1999. Modelling soil carbon dynamics with various cropping
564 sequences on the rolling pampas. *Agronomie* 19, 365–377.
565 <https://doi.org/10.1051/agro:19990504>
- 566 Batjes, N.H., 1996. Total carbon and nitrogen in the soils of the world. *European Journal of*
567 *Soil Science* 47, 151-163. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2389.1996.tb01386.x>
- 568 Bell, C., Carrillo, Y., Boot, C.M., Rocca, J.D., Pendall, E., Wallenstein, M.D., 2014.
569 Rhizosphere stoichiometry: Are C : N : P ratios of plants, soils, and enzymes conserved at
570 the plant species level? *New Phytologist* 201, 505–517. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nph.12531>
- 571 Bleuler, M., Farina R., Francaviglia, R., Di Bene, C., Napoli, R., Marchetti, A., 2017. Modelling
572 the impacts of different carbon sources on the soil organic carbon stock and CO₂ emissions
573 in the Foggia province (Southern Italy). *Agricultural Systems* 157, 258-268.
574 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2017.07.017>
- 575 Bohner, J., Koethe, R. Conrad, O., Gross, J., Ringeler, A., Selige, T., 2002. Soil
576 regionalisation by means of terrain analysis and process parameterisation. In: Micheli, E.,

- 577 Nachtergaele, F., Montanarella, L. (Eds.), Soil classification 2001. European Soil Bureau,
578 Research Report No. 7, EUR 20398 EN, Luxembourg, pp. 213-222.
- 579 Boehner, J., Selige, T., 2006. Spatial prediction of soil attributes using terrain analysis and
580 climate regionalisation. In: Boehner, J., McCloy, K.R., Strobl, J. (Eds.), SAGA - Analysis
581 and modelling applications. Goettinger Geographische Abhandlungen, Goettingen, pp. 13-
582 28.
- 583 Breiman, L., 2001. Random Forests. Machine Learning 45, 5-32.
584 <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1010933404324>
- 585 Brilli, L., Bechini, L., Bindi, M., Carozzi, M., Cavalli, D., Conant, R., Dorich, C.D., Doro, L.,
586 Ehrhardt, F., Farina, R., Ferrise, R., Fitton, N., Francaviglia, R., Grace, P., Iocola, I.,
587 Klumpp, K., Léonard, J., Martin, R., Massad, R.S., Recous, S., Seddaiu, G., Sharp, J., Smith,
588 P., Smith, W.N., Soussana, J-F., Bellocchi, G., 2017. Review and analysis of strengths and
589 weaknesses of agro-ecosystem models for simulating C and N fluxes. Science of the Total
590 Environment 598, 445-470. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.03.208>
- 591 Brisson, N., Gary, C., Justes, E., Roche, R., Mary, B., Ripoche, D., Zimmer, D., Sierra, J.,
592 Bertuzzi, P., Burger, P., Bussiere, F., Cabidoche, Y. M., Cellier, P., Debaeke, P., Gaudillere,
593 J. P., Henault, C., Maraux, F., Seguin, B., Sinoquet, H., 2003. An overview of the crop model
594 STICS. European Journal of Agronomy 18, 309–332. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1161-](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1161-0301(02)00110-7)
595 [0301\(02\)00110-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1161-0301(02)00110-7)
- 596 Brisson, N., Launay, M., Mary, B., Baudoin, N., 2008. Conceptual basis, formalizations and
597 parameterization of the STICS crop model. Editions Quae.
- 598 Brisson, N., Mary, B., Ripoche, D., Jeuffroy, M. H., Ruget, F., Nicoullaud, B., Gate, P.,
599 Devienne-Barret, F., Antonioletti, R., Durr, C., Richard, G., Beaudoin, N., Recous, S., Tayot,

- 600 X., Plenet, D., Cellier, P., Machet, J.-M., Meynard, J. M., Delécolle, R., 1998. STICS: A
601 generic model for the simulation of crops and their water and nitrogen balances. I. Theory
602 and parameterization applied to wheat and corn. *Agronomie* 18, 311–346.
603 <https://doi.org/10.1051/agro:19980501>
- 604 Chiti, T., Gardin, L., Perugini, L., Quarantino, R., Vaccari, F.P., Miglietta, F., Valentini, R.,
605 2012. Soil organic carbon stock assessment for the different cropland land uses in Italy.
606 *Biology and Fertility of Soils* 48, 9-17. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00374-011-0599-4>
- 607 Clivot, H., Mouny, J.-C., Duparque, A., Dinh, J.-L., Denoroy, P., Houot, S., Vertès, F.,
608 Trochard, R., Bouthier, A., Sagot, S., Mary, B., 2019. Modeling soil organic carbon
609 evolution in long-term arable experiments with AMG model. *Environmental Modelling &*
610 *Software* 118, 99–113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2019.04.004>
- 611 Coleman, K., Jenkinson, D.S., 1996. RothC-26.3 - A model for the turnover of carbon in soil.
612 In: Powlson, D.S., Smith, P., Smith, J.U. (eds.), *Evaluation of soil organic matter models*
613 *using existing long-term datasets*, NATO ASI Series I. Springer-Verlag, Heidelberg, pp.
614 237-246.
- 615 Coleman, K., Jenkinson, D.S., 1999. RothC-26.3, a model for the turnover of carbon in soil:
616 *Model description and user's guide*. Lawes Agricultural Trust, Harpenden, UK.
- 617 Conrad, O., Bechtel, B., Bock, M., Dietrich, H., Fischer, E., Gerlitz, L., Wehberg, J.,
618 Wichmann, V., Böhrer, J., 2015. System for Automated Geoscientific Analyses (SAGA) v.
619 2.1.4, *Geoscientific Model Development* 8, 1991-2007. [https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-8-](https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-8-1991-2015)
620 [1991-2015](https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-8-1991-2015)
- 621 Coucheney, E., Buis, S., Launay, M., Constantin, J., Mary, B., García de Cortázar-Atauri, I.,
622 Ripoche, D., Beaudoin, N., Ruget, F., Andrianarisoa, K.S., Le Bas, C., Justes, E., Léonard,

623 J., 2015. Accuracy, robustness and behavior of the STICS soil–crop model for plant, water
624 and nitrogen outputs: Evaluation over a wide range of agro-environmental conditions in
625 France. *Environmental Modelling & Software* 64, 177–190. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envso>
626 [ft.2014.11.024](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envso.ft.2014.11.024)

627 Cutler, D.R., Edwards, T.C., Beard, K.H., Cutler, A., Hess, K.T., Gibson, J., Lawler, J.J., 2007.
628 Random Forests for classification in ecology. *Ecology* 88, 2783-2792.
629 <https://doi.org/10.1890/07-0539.1>

630 Deng, Y., Wu, C., Li, M., Chen, R., 2015. RNDISI: A ratio normalized difference soil index for
631 remote sensing of urban/suburban environments. *International Journal of Applied Earth*
632 *Observation and Geoinformation* 39, 40–48. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2015.02.010>

633 Di Bene, C., Marchetti, A., Francaviglia, R., Farina, R., 2016. Soil organic carbon dynamics in
634 typical durum wheat-based crop rotations of Southern Italy. *Italian Journal of Agronomy* 11,
635 763. <https://doi.org/10.4081/ija.2016.763>

636 Díaz, C.A., Albers, A., Zamora-Ledezma, E., Hamelin, L., 2024. The interplay between
637 bioeconomy and the maintenance of long-term soil organic carbon stock in agricultural soils:
638 A systematic review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 189: 113890.
639 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2023.113890>

640 Ehrhardt, F., Soussana, J.-F., Bellocchi, G., Grace, P., McAuliffe, R., Recous, S., Sándor, R.,
641 Smith, P., Snow, V., de Antoni Migliorati, M., Basso, B., Bhatia, A., Brillì, L., Doltra, J.,
642 Dorich, C.D., Doro, L., Fitton, N., Giacomini, S.J., Grant, B., Harrison, M.T., Jones, S.K.,
643 Kirschbaum, Miko, U.F., Klumpp, K., Laville, P., Léonard, J., Liebig, M., Lieffering, M.,
644 Martin, R., Massad, R.S., Meier, E., Merbold, L., Moore, A.D., Myrگیotis, V., Newton, P.,
645 Pattey, E., Rolinski, S., Sharp, J., Smith, W.N., Wu, L., Zhang, Q., 2018. Assessing

646 uncertainties in crop and pasture ensemble model simulations of productivity and N₂O
647 emissions. *Global Change Biology* 24, e603-e616. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13965>

648 EU, 2013. Decision No 529/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 May
649 2013 on accounting rules on greenhouse gas emissions and removals resulting from activities
650 relating to land use, land-use change and forestry and on information concerning actions
651 relating to those activities. Available online at: [http://eur-](http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2013:165:0080:0097:EN:PDF)
652 [lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2013:165:0080:0097:EN:PDF](http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2013:165:0080:0097:EN:PDF)

653 Falloon, P. Jones, C.D., Cerri, C.E., Al-Adamat, R., Kamoni, P., Bhattacharyya, T., Paustian,
654 K.E., Killian, K., Coleman, K., Milne, E., 2007. Climate change and its impact on soil and
655 vegetation carbon storage in Kenya, Jordan, India and Brazil. *Agriculture, Ecosystems &*
656 *Environment* 122, 114-124. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2007.01.013>

657 Falloon, P., Smith, P., 2002. Simulating SOC changes in long-term experiments with RothC
658 and CENTURY: Model evaluation for a regional scale application. *Soil Use and*
659 *Management* 18, 101-111. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-2743.2002.tb00227.x>

660 Fantappiè, M., L'Abate, G., Schillaci, C., Costantini, E.A.C., 2023. Digital soil mapping of
661 Italy to map derived soil profiles with neural networks. *Geoderma Regional* 32, e00619.
662 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geodrs.2023.e00619>

663 Farina, R., Coleman, K., Whitmore, A.P., 2013. Modification of the RothC model for
664 simulations of soil organic C dynamics in dryland regions. *Geoderma* 200-201, 18-30.
665 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2013.01.021>

666 Farina, R., Marchetti, A., Francaviglia, R., Napoli, R., Di Bene, C., 2017. Modeling regional
667 soil C stocks and CO₂ emissions under Mediterranean cropping systems and soil types.

- 668 Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment 238, 128-141.
669 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2016.08.015>
- 670 Farina, R., Sándor, R., Abdalla, M., Álvaro-Fuentes, J., Bechini, L., Bolinder, M.A., Brillì, L.,
671 Chenu, C., Clivot, H., De Antoni Migliorati, M., Di Bene, C., Dorich, C.D., Ehrhardt, F.,
672 Ferchaud, F., Fitton, N., Francaviglia, R., Franko, U., Giltrap, D.L., Grant, B.B., Guenet, B.,
673 Harrison, M.T., Kirschbaum, M.U.F., Kuka, K., Kulmala, L., Liski, J., McGrath, M.J.,
674 Meier, E., Menichetti, L., Moyano, F., Nendel, C., Recous, S., Reibold, N., Shepherd, A.,
675 Smith, W.N., Smith, P., Soussana, J.F., Stella, T., Taghizadeh-Toosi, A., Tsutsikh, E.,
676 Bellocchi, G., 2021. Ensemble modelling, uncertainty and robust predictions of organic
677 carbon in long-term bare-fallow soils. *Global Change Biology* 27, 904-928.
678 <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.15441>
- 679 Gallant, J.C., Dowling, T.I., 2003. A multiresolution index of valley bottom flatness for
680 mapping depositional areas. *Water Resources Research* 39, 1347.
681 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1029/2002WR001426>
- 682 Gottschalk, P., Smith, J.U., Wattenbach, M., Bellarby, J., Stehfest, E., Arnell, N., Osborn, T.J.,
683 Jones, C., Smith, P., 2012. How will organic carbon stocks in mineral soils evolve under
684 future climate? Global projections using RothC for a range of climate change scenarios.
685 *Biogeosciences* 9, 3151–3171. <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-9-3151-2012>
- 686 Grimm, R., Behrens, T., Märker, M., Elsenbeer, H., 2008. Soil organic carbon concentrations
687 and stocks on Barro Colorado Island - Digital soil mapping using Random Forests analysis.
688 *Geoderma* 146, 102-113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2008.05.008>
- 689 Guo, L.B., Gifford, R.M., 2002. Soil carbon stocks and land use change: A meta analysis.
690 *Global Change Biology* 8, 345-360. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1354-1013.2002.00486.x>

- 691 Hengl, T., 2007. A practical guide to geostatistical mapping of environmental variables. EUR
692 22904 EN. Luxembourg (Luxembourg): Office for Official Publications of the European
693 Communities; 2007. JRC38153.
- 694 Hengl, T., Nussbaum, M., Wright, M.N., Heuvelink, G.B., Gräler, B., 2018. Random Forest as
695 a generic framework for predictive modeling of spatial and spatio-temporal variables. PeerJ
696 6, e5518. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.5518>
- 697 IPCC, 2006. 2006 IPCC guidelines for national greenhouse gas inventories. The National
698 Greenhouse Gas Inventories Program, Hayama, Kanagawa, Japan.
- 699 IUSS-WRB, 2014. World Reference Base for Soil Resources (2014). World Soil Resources
700 Reports, vol. 106. Rome: FAO, p. 181.
- 701 Jenkinson, D.S., Harris, H.C., Ryan, J., McNeill, M., Pilbeam, C.J., Coleman, K., 1999. Organic
702 matter turnover in a calcareous clay soil from Syria under a two-course cereal rotation. Soil
703 Biology and Biochemistry 31, 687-693. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0038-0717\(98\)00157-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0038-0717(98)00157-6)
- 704 Keenor, S.G., Rodrigues, A.F., Mao, L., Latawiec, A.E., Harwood, A.R., Reid, B.J., 2021.
705 Capturing a soil carbon economy. Royal Society Open Science 82, 02305.
706 <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.202305>
- 707 Keshtkar, H., Voigt, W., Alizadeh, E., 2017. Land cover classification with random forest
708 method using sentinel-1 satellite data. Journal of Environmental Management 196, 516-528.
709 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2017.02.066>
- 710 Lal, R., 2004. Soil carbon sequestration impacts on global climate change and food security.
711 Science 304, 1623-1627. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1097396>
- 712 Le Noël, J., Manzoni, S., Abramoff, R., Bölscher, T., Bruni, E., Cardinael, R., Ciais, P., Chenu,
713 C., Clivot, H., Derrien, D., Ferchaud, F., Garnier, P., Goll, D., Lashermes, G., Martin, M.,

714 Rasse, D., Rees, F., Sainte-Marie, J., Salmon, E., Schiedung, M., Schimel, J., Wieder, W.,
715 Abiven, S., Barré, P., Cécillon, L., Guenet, B., 2023. Soil organic carbon models need
716 independent time-series validation for reliable prediction. *Communications Earth &*
717 *Environment* 4, 158. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-023-00830-5>

718 Levassasseur, F., Mary, B., Christensen, B.T., Duparque, A., Ferchaud, F., Kätterer, T.,
719 Lagrange, H., Montenach, D., Resseguier, C., Houot, S., 2020. The simple AMG model
720 accurately simulates organic carbon storage in soils after repeated application of exogenous
721 organic matter. *Nutrient Cycling in Agroecosystems* 117, 215–229.
722 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10705-020-10065-x>

723 Li, J., Heap, A.D., 2014. Spatial interpolation methods applied in the environmental sciences:
724 A review. *Environmental Modelling & Software* 53, 173-189.
725 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2013.12.008>

726 Lugato, E., Bampa, F., Panagos, P., Montanarella, L., Jones, A., 2014. Potential carbon
727 sequestration of European arable soils estimated by modelling a comprehensive set of
728 management practices. *Global Change Biology* 20, 3557-3567.
729 <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12551>

730 Luo, Y., Ahlström, A., Allison, S. D., Batjes, N. H., Brovkin, V., Carvalhais, N., Chappell, A.,
731 Ciais, P., Davidson, E.A., Finzi, A., Georgiou, K., Guenet, B., Hararuk, O., Harden, J.W.,
732 He, Y., Hopkins, F., Jiang, L., Koven, C., Jackson, R.B., Jones, C.D., Lara, M.J., Liang, J.,
733 McGuire, A.D., Parton, W., Peng, C., Randerson, J.T., Salazar, A., Sierra, C.A., Smith, M.J.,
734 Tian, H., Todd-Brown, K.E.O., Torn, M., Van Groenigen, K.J., Wang, Y.P., West, T.O.,
735 Wei, Y., Wieder, W.R., Xia, J., Xu, X., Xu, X., Zhou, T., 2016. Toward more realistic

736 projections of soil carbon dynamics by Earth system models. *Global Biogeochemical Cycles*
737 30, 40-56. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2015GB005239>

738 Luo, Y., Melillo, J., Niu, S., Beier, C., Clark, J.S., Classen, A.T., Davidson, E., Dukes, J.S.,
739 Evans, R.D., Field, C.B., Czimczik, C.I., Keller, M., Kimball, B.A., Kueppers, L.M., Norby,
740 R.J., Pelini, S.L., Pendall, E., Rastetter, E., Six, J., Smith, M., Tjoelker, M.G., Torn, M.S.,
741 2011. Coordinated approaches to quantify long-term ecosystem dynamics in response to
742 global change. *Global Change Biology* 17, 843–854. [https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2010.02265.x)
743 [2486.2010.02265.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2010.02265.x)

744 Luo, Z., Wang, E., Sun, O. J., 2010. Can no-tillage stimulate carbon sequestration in agricultural
745 soils? A meta-analysis of paired experiments. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 139,
746 224-231. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2010.08.006>

747 Martin, M.P., Dimassi, B., Dobarco, M.R., Guenet, B., Arrouays, D., Angers, D.A., Blache, F.,
748 Huard, F., Soussana, J.-F., Pellerin, S., 2022. Feasibility of the 4 per 1000 aspirational target
749 for soil carbon: A case study for France. *Global Change Biology* 27, 2458-2477.
750 <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.15547>

751 Mary, B., Clivot, H., Blaszczyk, N., Labreuche, L., Ferchaud, F., 2020. Soil carbon storage and
752 mineralization rates are affected by carbon inputs rather than physical disturbance: Evidence
753 from a 47-year tillage experiment. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 299, 106972.
754 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2020.106972>

755 Minasny, B., Malone, B.P., McBratney, A.B., Angers, D.A., Arrouays, D., Chambers, A.,
756 Chaplot, V., Chen, Z.-S., Cheng, K., Das, B.S., Field, D.J., Gimona, A., Hedley, C.B., Hong,
757 S.Y., Mandal, B., Marchant, B.P., Martin, M., McConkey, B.G., Mulder, V.L., O'Rourke,
758 S., Richer-de-Forges, A.C. Odeh, I., Padarian, J., Paustian, K., Pan, G., Poggio, L., Savin, I.,

- 759 Stolbovoy, V., Stockmann, U., Sulaeman, Y., Tsui, C.-C., Vågen, T.-G., Van Wesemael, B.,
760 Winowiecki, L., 2017. Soil carbon 4 per mille. *Geoderma* 292, 59-86.
761 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2017.01.002>
- 762 Mirchooli, F., Kiani-Harchegani, M., Darvishan, A.K., Falahatkar, S., Sadeghi, S.H., 2020.
763 Spatial distribution dependency of soil organic carbon content to important environmental
764 variables. *Ecological Indicators* 116, 106473. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2020.106473>
- 765 Mondini, C., Coleman, K., Whitmore, A.P., 2012. Spatially explicit modelling of changes in
766 soil organic C in agricultural soils in Italy, 2001-2100: Potential for compost amendment.
767 *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 153, 24-32.
768 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2012.02.020>
- 769 Ogle, S.M., Jay Breidt, F., Paustian, K., 2005. Agricultural management impacts on soil organic
770 carbon storage under moist and dry climatic conditions of temperate and tropical regions.
771 *Biogeochemistry* 72, 87–121. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10533-004-0360-2>
- 772 Olaya, V., 2009. Chapter 6 - Basic land-surface parameters. In: Hengl, T., Reuter, H.I. (Eds.),
773 *Geomorphometry: Concepts, software, applications. Developments in Soil Science*, 33, 141-
774 169. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0166-2481\(08\)00006-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0166-2481(08)00006-8)
- 775 Prasad, A.M., Iverson, L.R., Liaw, A., 2006. Newer classification and regression tree
776 techniques: Bagging and Random Forests for ecological prediction. *Ecosystems* 9, 181-199.
777 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10021-005-0054-1>
- 778 Prima, O.D.A., Echigo, A., Yokoyama, R., Yoshida, T., 2006. Supervised landform
779 classification of Northeast Honshu from DEM-derived thematic maps. *Geomorphology* 78,
780 373–386. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2006.02.005>

- 781 Pulina, A., Ferrise, R., Mula, L., Brilli, L., Giglio, L., Iocola, I., Ventrella, D., Zavattaro, L.,
782 Grignani, C., Roggero, P.P., 2022. The ability of crop models to predict soil organic carbon
783 changes in a maize cropping system under contrasting fertilization and residues
784 management: Evidence from a long-term experiment. *Italian Journal of Agronomy* 17, 2179.
785 <https://doi.org/10.4081/ija.2022.2179>
- 786 Riggers, C., Poeplau, C., Don, A., Bamminger, C., Höper, H., Dechow, R., 2019. Multi-model
787 ensemble improved the prediction of trends in soil organic carbon stocks in German
788 croplands. *Geoderma* 345, 17-30. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2019.03.014>
- 789 Rodrigues, L., Hardy, B., Huyghebeart, B., Fohrafellner, J., Fornara, D., Barančíková, G.,
790 Bárcena, T.G., De Boever, M., Di Bene, C., Feizienė, D., Kätterer, T., Laszlo, P., O’Sullivan,
791 L., Seitz, D., Leifeld, J., 2021. Achievable agricultural soil carbon sequestration across
792 Europe from country-specific estimates. *Global Change Biology* 27, 6363–6380.
793 <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.15897>
- 794 Rumpel, C., Kögel-Knabner, I., 2011. Deep soil organic matter - a key but poorly understood
795 component of terrestrial C cycle. *Plant and Soil* 338, 143-158.
796 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-010-0391-5>
- 797 Saffih-Hdadi, K., Mary, B., 2008. Modeling consequences of straw residues export on soil
798 organic carbon. *Soil Biology & Biochemistry* 40, 594–607. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilb>
799 [io.2007.08.022](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilb.2007.08.022)
- 800 Sándor, R., Ehrhardt, F., Grace, P., Recous, S., Smith, P., Snow, V., Soussana, J.-F., Basso, B.,
801 Bhatia, A., Brilli, L., Doltra, J., Dorich, C.D., Doro, L., Fitton, N., Grant, B., Harrison, M.T.,
802 Kirschbaum, M.U.F., Klumpp, K., Laville, P., Léonard, J., Martin, R., Massad, R.S., Moore,
803 A., Myrگیotis, V., Pattey, E., Rolinski, R., Sharp, J., Skiba, U., Smith, W., Wu, L., Zhang,

- 804 Q., Bellocchi, G., 2020. Ensemble modelling of carbon fluxes in grasslands and croplands.
805 Field Crops Research 252, 107791. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fcr.2020.107791>
- 806 Shi, Z., Crowell, S., Luo, Y., Moore, B., 2018. Model structures amplify uncertainty in
807 predicted soil carbon responses to climate change. Nature Communication 9, 2171.
808 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-04526-9>
- 809 Six, J., Conant, R.T., Paul, E.A., Paustian, K., 2002. Stabilization mechanisms of soil organic
810 matter: implications for C-saturation of soils. Plant and Soil 241, 155-176.
- 811 Smith, P., House, J.I., Bustamante, M., Sobocká, J., Harper, R., Pan, G., , Kamari, J., 2016.
812 Global change pressures on soils from land use and management. Global Change Biology
813 22, 1008-1028. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13068>
- 814 Smith, P., Powlson, D.S., Smith, J.U., Falloon, P., Coleman, K., 2001. Meeting Europe's climate
815 change commitments: quantitative estimates of the potential for carbon mitigation by
816 agriculture. Global Change Biology 6, 525-539. [https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-](https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2486.2000.00331.x)
817 [2486.2000.00331.x](https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2486.2000.00331.x)
- 818 Smith, P., Smith, J.U., Powlson, D.S., McGill, W.B., Arah, J.R.M., Chertov, O.G., Coleman,
819 K., Franko, U., Frolking, S., Jenkinson, D.S., Jensen, L.S., Kelly, R.H., Klein-Gunnewiek,
820 H., Komarov, A.S., Li, C., Molina, J.A.E., Mueller, T., Parton, W.J., Thornley, J.H.M.,
821 Whitmore, A.P., 1997. A comparison of the performance of nine soil organic matter models
822 using datasets from seven long-term experiments. Geoderma 81, 153-225.
823 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-7061\(97\)00087-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-7061(97)00087-6)
- 824 Smith, J., Gottschalk, P., Bellarby, J., Chapman, S., Lilly, A., Towers, W., Bell, J., Coleman,
825 K., Nayak, D., Richards, M., Hillier, J., Flynn, H., Wattenbach, M., Aitkenhead, M.,
826 Yeluripati, J., Farmer, J., Milne, R., Thomson, A., Evans, C., Whitmore, A., Falloon, P.,

827 Smith, P., 2010a. Estimating changes in national soil carbon stocks using ECOSSE - A new
828 model that includes upland organic soils. Part I. Model description and uncertainty in
829 national scale simulations of Scotland. *Climate Research*, 45, 179–192.
830 <https://doi.org/10.3354/cr00899>

831 Smith, J., Gottschalk, P., Bellarby, J., Chapman, S., Lilly, A., Towers, W., Bell, J., Coleman,
832 K., Nayak, D., Richards, M., Hillier, J., Flynn, H., Wattenbach, M., Aitkenhead, M.,
833 Yeluripati, J., Farmer, J., Milne, R., Thomson, A., Evans, C., Whitmore, A., Falloon, P.,
834 Smith, P., 2010b. Estimating changes in national soil carbon stocks using ECOSSE – A new
835 model that includes upland organic soils. Part II. Application in Scotland. *Climate Research*
836 45, 193–205. <https://doi.org/10.3354/cr00902>

837 Snyder, C.S., Bruulsema, T.W., Jensen, T.L., Fixen, P.E., 2009. Review of greenhouse gas
838 emissions from crop production systems and fertilizer management effects. *Agriculture,*
839 *Ecosystems & Environment* 133, 247-266. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2009.04.021>

840 Tarquini S., Isola I., Favalli M., Battistini A., Dotta G., 2023. TINITALY, a digital elevation
841 model of Italy with a 10 meters cell size (Version 1.1). Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e
842 Vulcanologia (INGV). <https://doi.org/10.13127/tinitaly/1.1>

843 Todd-Brown, K.E., Randerson, J.T., Post, W.M., Hoffman, F.M., Tarnocai, C., Schuur, E.A.,
844 Allison, S.D., 2013. Causes of variation in soil carbon predictions from CMIP5 Earth system
845 models and comparison with observations. *Biogeosciences* 10, 1717-1736.
846 <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-10-1717-2013>

847 UNFCCC, 1998. Kyoto protocol to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate
848 Change. Available online at: <http://www.unfccc.int/resource/docs/convkp/kpeng.pdf>.

- 849 Wieder, W.R., Bonan, G., Allison, S., 2013. Global soil carbon projections are improved by
850 modelling microbial processes. *Nature Climate Change* 3, 909–912.
851 <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate1951>
- 852 Wieder, W.R., Grandy, A.S., Kallenbach, C.M., Bonan, G.B., 2014. Integrating microbial
853 physiology and physio-chemical principles in soils with the Microbial-MIneral Carbon
854 Stabilization (MIMICS) model. *Biogeosciences* 11, 3899-3917. [https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-](https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-11-3899-2014)
855 [11-3899-2014](https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-11-3899-2014)
- 856 Wilson, J.P., Gallant, J.C., 2000. *Terrain analysis - principles and applications*. John Wiley &
857 Sons, Inc., New York.
- 858 Wright, M.N., Ziegler, A., 2017. Ranger: A fast implementation of random forests for high
859 dimensional data in C++ and R. *Journal of Statistical Software* 77, 1–17.
860 <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v077.i01>
- 861 Xiao, T., Ran, F., Li, Z., Wang, S., Nie, X., Liu, Y., Yang, C., Tan, M., Feng, S., 2023. Sediment
862 organic carbon dynamics response to land use change in diverse watershed anthropogenic
863 activities. *Environment International* 172, 107788.
864 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2023.107788>
- 865 Xiao, J., Shen, Y., Tateishi, R., Bayaer, W., 2006. Development of topsoil grain size index for
866 monitoring desertification in arid land using remote sensing. *International Journal of Remote*
867 *Sensing* 27, 2411–2422. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01431160600554363>
- 868 Yagasaki, Y., Shirato, Y., 2014. Assessment on the rates and potentials of soil organic carbon
869 sequestration in agricultural lands in Japan using a process-based model and spatially
870 explicit land-use change inventories-Part 1: Historical trend and validation based on nation-

- 871 wide soil monitoring. *Biogeosciences* 11, 4429-4442. [https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-11-4429-](https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-11-4429-2014)
872 [2014](https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-11-4429-2014)
- 873 Yokoyama, R., Shlrasawa, M., Richard, P, 2002. Visualizing topography by openness: A new
874 application of image processing to digital elevation models. *Photogrammetric Engineering*
875 *and Remote Sensing*, 68, 257–266. <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:9906987>
- 876 Zhang, W., Ricketts, T.H., Kremen, C., Carney, K., Swinton, S.M., 2007. Ecosystem services
877 and dis-services to agriculture. *Ecological Economics* 64, 253-260.
878 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2007.02.024>

